

Phytochemical Studies on the Genus *Crotalaria* : Part IX. Integerrimine and Usaramine from *Crotalaria incana* Linn

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Integerrimine and usaramine have been isolated from the seeds of *Crotalaria incana*. They have been identified by mixed m.p. and i.r. and n.m.r comparison with authentic samples.

Crotalaria incana (Leguminosae) is a shrub which grows in Kumaon hills at a height of about 5,000 ft. The whole plant is clothed with fine spreading silky hair¹. The plant is reported to have antibiotic properties². The alkaloids integerrimine and usaramine which are present in *Crotalaria incana* have shown marked hypotensive effect in anaesthetized dogs. They also produce relaxant effect and exhibit spasmolytic property against known spasmogens in smooth muscles of different species of animals³.

Adams and Van Duuren⁴ published the occurrence of integerrimine in the seeds of *C. incana*. Recently Mattocks⁵ recorded the isolation of anacrotine and absence of integerrimine from the stem, leaf and flowers. Our findings have shown the presence of usaramine which has previously been reported to occur in *C. usaramoensis* E. G. Baker⁶, *C. mucronata* Desv.⁷ and *C. brevifolia*⁷, in addition to integerrimine. The alkaloid mucronatine reported by Bhacca and Sharma⁸ appears to be usaramine.

The dehusked powdered seeds (590 g) were defatted with n. hexane and subsequently extracted with methanol in a Soxhlet apparatus. The methanol was distilled off under reduced pressure when semisolid dark brown residue resulted. On TLC, using silica gel G (slurry made with *N*/10 sodium hydroxide) and chloroform-methanol-ammonia (85 : 14 : 1) as the solvent system showed two spots with R_f 0.61 and 0.31. The residue was treated with 0.5 *N* sulphuric acid, filtered and the filtrate was reduced with zinc dust. The acidic solution was washed with chloroform, basified with ammonia and extracted with petroleum ether and subsequently with chloroform.

Removal of petroleum ether yielded integerrimine (305 mg) melting point and mixed m.p. 169–70° (reported⁹ for integerrimine 172°). Prepared picrate m.p. and m.m.p. 210–211° (integerrimine picrate⁹ 213°).

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The chloroform fraction removal of solvent gave a crude mixture (840 mg) of two alkaloids. The mixture could not be separated by fractional crystallisations. It was charged over ethylacetate deactivated alumina (30 g) and eluted with benzene, benzene-chloroform, chloroform and chloroform-methanol. Fractions eluted with chloroform-methanol (99 : 1) yielded further quantity of integerrimine (170 mg) and fractions eluted with chloroform-methanol (98 : 2) gave another pale yellow waxy alkaloid (130 mg) whose TLC and paper chromatographic behaviour in four different solvent systems agreed with that of usaramine. Any attempt to crystallise the base resulted further blackening of its colour. It was again purified through alumina column and the base obtained was washed with 0.5% sodium hydroxide to give crystalline material, m.p. and m.m.p. 180–181° (usaramine⁶ m.p. 182.5–183.5). The I.R. (KBr) of the base was identical to that of usaramine. Its NMR (60 MCS, CDCl₃) fully agreed with the NMR of usaramine.

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